

Maternal knowledge of Sickle Cell Disease and its Predictors in Southeast Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Sickle cell disease (SCD) is an inherited disorder of haemoglobin and the most common genetic disease in sub-Saharan Africa. The knowledge of mothers about the hereditary basis of SCD in our locality is yet to be ascertained. **Objectives:** The study determined the knowledge of mothers regarding its cause /inheritance pattern and identified demographic factors related to it. **Methods:** This was a descriptive cross-sectional study. A total of 793 mothers attending the antenatal and postnatal clinics of a tertiary hospital in southeast Nigeria were consecutively recruited and data was collected using a pretested questionnaire. **Results:** The modal age group of the mothers was 21-30 years. Almost all were married 788 (99.4%). More than half (59.1%) had a university education. A majority, 565 (71.2%) are employed while 228 (28.8%) are unemployed. Those whose spouses have university education were 71.1%. Almost all participants (95%) were Christians. The majority (70.9%) had good knowledge of sickle cell disease, of which 67.3% knew that sickle cell disease is inherited from both parents while 3.5% knew it is a blood disorder. Mothers' and fathers' educational levels were good predictors of knowledge about sickle cell disease ($P=0.0001$). **Conclusion:** This study showed a good knowledge of sickle cell mode of inheritance among mothers. However, there is need for more emphasis on promoting sickle cell education by including the subject in the health education curriculum of schools at all levels in the country and also community education programmes to reach those outside the school system. Adoption of religious bodies as critical stakeholders in sickle cell disease prevention and education will enhance awareness about sickle cell disease.

Key words: Education, Maternal Knowledge, sickle cell disease.

INTRODUCTION

Sickle cell disease is a group of inherited disorders characterized by recurrent episodes of painful crises¹. It results from the inheritance of haemoglobinS (HbS) from both parents either in the homozygous state or with another abnormal gene in heterozygous state. Sickle cell anaemia is a

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severe form of the disease and it accounts for about 83% of all newborns with SCD². Nigeria parades the highest disease burden in the world with a carrier prevalence rate of about 20-30% and disease prevalence of 2-3%³. Sickle cell disease is a disease of public health concern and globally, over 300,000 babies are born annually with sickle cell disease¹.

Curative treatment for SCD with allogeneic stem cell transplantation is reserved for severe disease and unaffordable for most patients in our environment⁴. The current management plan for SCD should focus more on prevention through mass education and genetic counselling⁵.

Continued and uncontrolled marriage among sickle cell carriers and interventions such as newborn screening and provision of comprehensive care lead to more adults with sickle cell disease^{5,6}. Understanding the inheritance pattern of SCD is key to prevention and reduction of disease burden.

WHO has recommended that improving awareness, genetic counselling, and testing to prevent SCD is a public health intervention to reduce the burden of SCD⁷.

Accurate maternal knowledge of SCD is a key factor affecting their attitude towards the disease⁸. In Nigeria, there is an inequality in girl child education compared to their male counterparts. This inequality does not necessarily change in adulthood⁹. Statistics available show that 774 million illiterate adults worldwide, 64 percent are women¹⁰. The 2012 Gender in Nigeria report revealed that Nigerian women with less education were less likely to seek antenatal care¹¹. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) uses education as its target for women empowerment and gender equality¹². In Nigeria so many SCD awareness and control programmes have been put in place to educate the populace to reduce the disease burden. Many researchers have studied the knowledge level of SCD in different populations, especially secondary school students and undergraduates, but there is a paucity of studies on the maternal population^{8, 13,14,15,16}. It is important that mothers have appropriate knowledge about sickle cell disease to guide prenatal diagnosis,

neonatal screening and subsequent counselling of their children about compatible reproductive partners. This study therefore sought to assess the current knowledge of sickle cell disease among mothers and identify demographic factors related to it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design: This was a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out among women attending the antenatal and postnatal care clinics at Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital, Abakaliki (AEFUTHA) Ebonyi State. AEFUTHA is a 700-bedded tertiary health facility located in Ebonyi State southeast Nigeria. It serves the surrounding states of Cross River, Abia, and Enugu states. Attendees were consecutively recruited for the study.

Sample size calculation: The Sample size formula for cross-sectional design was employed. Using a standard normal deviate of 1.96, which corresponds to an alpha level of 0.05, a proportion of maternal knowledge of sickle cell disease of 48.3% from a similar Nigerian study by Babalola *et al* (17). The Precision level of 4% and a nonresponse rate of 20%, a sample size of 793 was appropriate for the study.

Data management: Data on demographic variables (age, marital status, educational level, and employment status), perception, and knowledge of sickle cell disease were obtained from the respondents in the study with the use of pretested questionnaires. Data entry employed Microsoft Excel software, after which the entered data were exported to IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 21.0 for statistical analysis.

The responses to the perception of sickle cell disease were presented in a horizontal frequency bar chart. Respondents who identified sickle cell disease as a blood disorder and/or inherited from both parents were classified as 'knowledgeable'. Knowledge of sickle cell disease was a dependent variable and categorized as knowledgeable/not knowledgeable. The demographic information comprised the independent variables. Comparison of knowledge of

sickle cell disease across demographic findings was performed using Pearson's Chi Square or Fisher's exact test when the expected cell value was below five in at least twenty percent of the crosstab cells. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$. Significant variables on cross tabulation were entered into a binary logistic regression model. Adjusted odds ratios were determined at the 95% level to assess the strength of association.

Ethical issues: This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital Abakaliki. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

RESULTS

A total of 793 participants filled and returned their questionnaires over a period of 8 weeks of the study. Their age range was between 20-50 years with a modal age group of 21-30 years. Almost all were married 788 (99.4%), while 4 (0.5%) are single and one (0.1%) is a widow. Four hundred and sixty-nine (59.1%) participants had university education, 170 (21.4%) had GTC/NCE as their highest educational level, while those with secondary and primary school as their highest level of education, were 110 (13.9%) and 41 (5.2%) respectively. Only 3 (0.4%) of the participants did not have any formal education. A majority, 565 (71.2%) are employed while 228 (28.8%) are unemployed. Those whose spouses have university education accounted for 71.1% of the participants. Almost all participants (95%) are Christians. (Table 1)

A majority (70.9%) of the participants had good knowledge of sickle cell disease (Figure 1). Out of this, 67.3% knew that sickle cell disease is inherited from both parents while 3.5% knew it is a blood disorder. More than a quarter (29.1%) does not have good knowledge about sickle cell disease. Out of this, 7.9% of them believe that sickle cell disease is a contagious disease, 2.6% believe that it is inherited

from mother alone, 0.1% believe it's from the father alone while 0.1% believe that sickle cell disease is caused by witchcraft. (Figure 2)

As shown in Table 2, analyses revealed that mothers' and fathers' educational levels were good predictors of knowledge about sickle cell disease ($P = 0.0001$). However, the fathers' educational level had a stronger relationship with SCD knowledge than mothers' educational level. (Table 3).

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of study participants

Variables (N=793)	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Age groups		
≤20	18	2.3
21-30	418	52.7
31-40	342	43.1
41-50	15	1.9
Religion		
Christianity	789	99.5
Islam	4	0.5
Marital status		
Married	788	99.4
Single	4	0.5
Widowed	1	0.1
Educational level		
No formal education	3	13.9
Primary education	41	5.2
Secondary education	170	21.4
GTC/NCE	110	13.9
University education	469	59.1
Educational level of spouse (N=775)*		
No formal education	3	0.4
Primary education	34	4.4
Secondary education	134	17.3
GTC/NCE	53	6.8
University education	551	71.1
Employment status		
Employed	565	71.2
Unemployed	228	28.8

*18 mothers did not know the educational status of their spouses

Table 2: Comparison of knowledge on sickle cell disease across demographic findings of mothers in the study

Demographic findings	Knowledge on Sickle Cell Disease		Total
	Knowledgeable	Not Knowledgeable	
Age			
≤ 20years	11 (61.1)	7 (38.9)	18 (100.0)
21-30 years	291 (69.6)	127 (30.4)	418 (100.0)
31-40 years	251 (73.4)	91 (26.6)	342 (100.0)
41-50 years	9 (60.0)	6 (40.0)	15 (100.0)
	<i>Chi square=3.060; p-value=0.382</i>		
Marital status			
Married	559 (70.9)	229 (29.1)	788 (100.0)
Single	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	4 (100.0)
Widowed	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)
	<i>Chi square=1.510; p-value=0.705</i>		
Employment status			
Employed	404 (71.5)	161 (28.5)	565 (100.0)
Unemployed	158 (69.3)	70 (30.7)	228 (100.0)
	<i>Chi square=0.383; p-value=0.536</i>		
Level of education			
No formal education	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	3 (100.0)
Primary	23 (56.1)	18 (43.9)	41 (100.0)
Secondary	95 (55.9)	75 (44.1)	170 (100.0)
GTC/NCE	77 (70.0)	33 (30.0)	110 (100.0)
University education	366 (78.0)	103 (22.0)	469 (100.0)
	<i>Fisher's Exact=36.789; p-value=0.0001*</i>		
Spouse level of education**			
No formal education	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	3 (100.0)
Primary	18 (52.9)	16 (47.1)	34 (100.0)
Secondary	82 (61.2)	52 (38.8)	134 (100.0)
GTC/NCE	32 (60.4)	21 (39.6)	53 (100.0)
Tertiary	422 (76.6)	129 (23.4)	551 (100.0)
	<i>Fisher's Exact=24.676; p-value=0.0001*</i>		

*Statistically significant **N=755

Table 3. Logistic regression showing predictors of knowledge of SCD among study population

Factors	Coefficient(B)	Adjusted Odds ratio (AOR)	95% CI	p value
Level of education				
Secondary and higher	-0.208	0.81	0.34 – 1.94	0.640
Below secondary level		1.00		
Spouse level of education				
Secondary and higher	1.04	2.83	1.23 – 6.52	0.014*
Below secondary level		1.00		

*Statistically significant, CI – Confidence interval

Figure 1: Proportion of mothers with knowledge on sickle cell disease in the study

Figure 2: Maternal perception on causes of sickle cell disease

DISCUSSION

Maternal perception and knowledge of SCD are key factors that influence their attitude towards the disease. It is an important variable that affects the acceptability and practice of genetic counselling, prenatal diagnosis and newborn screening¹⁷.

Good knowledge of the mode of inheritance of sickle cell disease was expressed by almost 70% of women in this study. This is desirable for a country with a high burden of sickle cell disease and efforts should be intensified to maintain it through continuous public health education. Contrary to our findings, similar studies in the South-south and southwest regions of Nigeria by Babalola et al and Odunvun *et al* reported that only 23.3% and 48.3% of mothers respectively knew that sickle cell is inherited from both parents.^{18,19}

Being a tertiary care center, the mothers in our study were required to do genotype tests during their first antenatal visit and they also received health education and counselling services as part of the health package during antenatal clinic visits. The antenatal health education could have contributed to the good knowledge of sickle cell disease inheritance seen in this study. These services may not be available for women who seek care at private/faith-based and primary health centres where specialist care with the full complement of counselling skills, diagnostics, and other services may not be available as alluded to by Hasan et al¹⁹. Another key factor for this good knowledge of SCD in south-eastern Nigeria may be attributed to premarital genetic counselling and testing for haemoglobin genotypes which is a mandatory prerequisite for most church weddings. Christianity is the predominant religion in southeast Nigeria and many churches have premarital genotype screening and counselling as one of their regulations. The majority of participants in this study are Christians and this could have played a role. To support this, Abubakar *et al* established a significant association between religion and knowledge of SCD in their study.⁸ Adoption of this strategy by other religious groups as requirement before marriage could assist in reducing the burden of SCD in Nigeria since marriages between genotype incompatibility couples

are discouraged²⁰. A previous study has documented the role of religious organisations in the awareness and prevention of SCD.²¹

Moreover, the outcome of our study may be a reflection of the knowledge base of the population according to a report by Ugwu, who noted that almost 60% of their study population of students in a south-eastern university had a good knowledge of sickle cell disease inheritance²². This can be the outcome of vigorous public health enlightenment programmes by stakeholders in this locality.

Knowledge is power. Over 70% of the women in our study had tertiary level of education which could have empowered them to acquire and comprehend the correct information about the cause of sickle cell disease unlike the mothers interrogated by Babalola *et al*. whose majority attained secondary school level of education¹⁷. Our study also demonstrated that mothers and their spouses with tertiary level of education had better knowledge of SCD than those with lower levels of education. This finding is consistent with the previous study by Babalola *et al*, Daak et al, and Boada et al which showed that higher educational level of the mother and father is correlated with good knowledge and healthy perception of SCD^{17,23-24}. In another related study, Olatona *et al* concluded that post-interventional knowledge of sickle cell disease increased by 64.1% and attitude towards sickle cell disease increased by 11.9% only in the intervention group¹⁷. The influence of the educational status of mothers on good knowledge of SCD in our study is probably a reflection of the general finding in the population where studies have shown that students and undergraduates have a good knowledge of sickle cell disease mode of inheritance^{13,14}. Education helps men and women have the right knowledge and good perception about SCD and release their potential for good decision making¹³. In contrast, however, another study found that there was a deficiency in the knowledge about sickle cell disease and its prevention among undergraduates of a tertiary institution in Kano⁸. This has been attributed to poor educational exposure, misconceptions, myths, and religious

influences. Surprisingly, also, Adewoyin *et al's* study among National youth service members in Benin revealed that only 17.8% had good knowledge of sickle cell disease inheritance despite the high level of awareness¹⁵. This testifies to the disparity in awareness about SCD and the correct mode of inheritance which is the key to its prevention.

In Nigeria, health education is taught as part of civic education in secondary schools. The curriculum should be revised by stakeholders to ensure that the information provided will give learners the needed information about common health conditions in the populace including SCD which is the foremost inheritable disease in Nigeria. There should be a focused health education on the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of SCD in our educational system. Education helps to demystify myths and misconceptions about sickle cell disease.

Limitations of the study

The main limitation of this study is that the participants were all from one clinic and the results will not be generalizable. Also the study did not interrogate how the fathers' educational level influenced the SCD knowledge in the mothers. Despite this limitation, to the best of my knowledge, my study is the first of its kind in Ebonyi state which is designated educationally disadvantaged.

CONCLUSION

This study showed a good knowledge of sickle cell mode of inheritance among mothers who attended antenatal and postnatal care in a tertiary health centre. The majority of the mothers in the study and their spouses have attained tertiary level education and almost all the mothers are Christians. There is a need for more emphasis on health education through programmes promoting sickle cell education by including the subject in the health education curriculum of schools at all levels in the country. Mass media and community awareness programmes can help educate women who may not have the opportunity to attain formal education before getting

married and having babies. The adoption of religious bodies as critical stakeholders in sickle cell disease prevention and education will enhance awareness about sickle cell disease and counselling for intending couples to make informed decisions.

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Conflicts of Interest: None to declare

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